

Flemish Research Data Network Knowledge Hub

History 2021-2023

FRDN.

The Knowledge Hub of the Flemish Research Data Network is a network for and by data stewards and research data management (RDM) professionals who support researchers. The goal of the Knowledge Hub is to share RDM expertise, practices and tools, collaborate in training and education and reflect on career paths in RDM support.

Getting started in 2021

The Knowledge Hub started up with an online kick-off meeting on 25 February 2021 with 41 participants from 22 research institutions, where the context of Flemish Open Science policy was described, and inspiration was provided by examples like the Landelijk Coördinatiepunt Research Data Management (LCRDM) from the Netherlands. Interactive questions showed two third of people to be in a research supporting role, and others in an IT and infrastructure or policy role; and to be in this role for at least one year. A programme committee consisting of five people was set up, coordinated by a team of FOSB Open Science coordinators at FWO.

Lunchtime sessions online

With a start-up in the midst of the COVID pandemic, in the first year all activities had to be organised online and the decision was to hold monthly lunch time session of one hour on topics of interest to the community of data stewards. Suggestions for topics were elicited from the community itself.

The format consisted of one person of the programme committee taking the lead to organise a session, inviting 2-3 data stewards or researchers to give short presentations on their expertise or approach towards the chosen data management topic. A document with challenges, questions and responses was each time compiled to facilitate interaction with the audience. For several sessions a blog post was written up afterwards. Presentations and blogs for the ten lunch time sessions organised so far remain available on the [Knowledge Hub Basecamp](#).

Supporting researchers with DMPs, April 2021

Data stewards from various institutions shared their approach to support researchers with data management plans through website guidance, training sessions and one-on-one talks with researchers. The importance of taking time to talk with researchers came out as of prime importance.

	Data type	How created/ source	Format	Estimated volume
1. RESEARCHER	Existing data	Cloud (EMBL) database; patient information and clinical data collected during the trial (clinical and sequencing data)	Database owned and managed by COIC (EMBL); from various clinical data centres	MultiGAs
2. RESEARCHER	Generation of new data	Transcriptomic blood samples; clinical: molecular data (biobanks and relative values resulting from biomarker measurements); DNA genotyping data	Raw data: originates from sequencing-based assays, FASTQ, BAM sequencing (sequentially mapping generated reads from different blood samples for assay on 450 samples (200 patients, 15 time points))	See below* jifs
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the research will generate experimental data of different types including computational (molecular modelling results), experimental (NMR, MS, purified proteins), sequences and constructs (e.g. novel enzymes and oligonucleotides).

Data repositories, May 2021

The European data repository landscape was presented for Humanities, Engineering and Life and Marine Sciences. Participants agreed that trusted and FAIR-enabling discipline-specific repositories provide essential services to researchers, making it easier to put FAIR-compliant long-term preservation of research data into practice. The need for a Flemish 'white list' of approved data repositories to support open science was highlighted. And with person-related data being prevalent in life sciences and humanities, the lack of European data repositories to accommodate sharing such data with adequate security and legal provisions, was recognized, showing the need for a Flemish archiving solution.

Open Science in Horizon Europe, June & December 2021

Open Science becomes embedded across Horizon Europe. So what exactly are the requirements and how can we implement them? We looked forward towards the mandatory and recommended Open Science practices and explored the amended DMP for Horizon Europe.

What do you take away from this event? What did you most appreciate? Be as specific as possible.

- Quick walkthrough the Horizon Europe DMP
- Open Science gains speed!
- Key differences between H2020 and HEU about OA and RDM
- Getting to know this network
- I really liked the summary of the Horizon Europe program and the overall 'things to come' vibes.
- Overview of new requirements
- It's still early days, but nice to have an overview already
- I'm glad I was updated on new developments.
- key differences

Data Horror Escape room, September 2021

We played this online game created in the Netherlands that prompts discussions on RDM concepts in a fun way, as you need to solve several puzzles to escape from the room.

Electronic Lab Notebooks, October 2021

During this session the variety of Electronic Lab Notebooks (ELNs) that exist were discussed and the way to choose a suitable ELN for an institution, with a practical demo of ELabFTW and Signals Notebook given. The benefits of using an ELN is structured and time-stamped documentation and metadata, easy collaboration, user-friendly searchability and prevention of data loss. In particular, it facilitates good documentation and organisation required for Open Science. The recommendation for institutions is to promote a few diverse ELNs, rather than implement a single solution. Most efficient seems one or two generic ELNs and one or two discipline-specific ELNs that are user-friendly and do not require much training. ELNs are not limited to the 'hard' sciences. For humanities research Open

Science Framework (OSF) can be used. A poll amongst participants showed that frequently used ELNs are SLIMS, Signals, ELabFTW, OSF, Castor, Benchling, Lab Guru, Labfolder and Findings; with Signals, ELabFTW and OSF used in several Flemish institutions.

Metadata, January 2022

How a researcher records metadata is more important to describe in a DMP than knowing which standard to use. A priority for researchers is to add metadata to their datasets that explains clearly what the data mean. Metadata play a role in making datasets Findable, Interoperable and Reusable.

Key messages are to start as much as possible from existing commonly used standards, to start simple, with practical examples and extend later, and to use technologies that researchers know.

Research software management, March 2022

Code needs comments. That doesn't mean it needs to be posted on Facebook. It's about documentation. In this session we learned about tools and services for software

management and that FAIR workflows make FAIR software. GitHub and Gitbucket are used to share code. Archiving and citing code is easily done using Zenodo, with a suitable licence.

Encryption, April 2022

Encryption is the act of transforming a piece of information into an unintelligible form using a set of steps and a key or passphrase. We learned about file, disk and transport encryption and open source tools to use for this. Encryption is used in data management to protect and store sensitive data, to protect devices at risk of loss or theft, and to send data over untrusted networks. With as key message that all networks should be considered untrusted.

Encryption is the act of transforming a piece of information (clear text) into an unintelligible form (cypher text), using a fixed set of steps (encryption algorithm). In addition to the clear text, an algorithm usually requires additional input, which is to be kept confidential (secret, passphrase or key).

RDM practical implementation in a project, May 2022

Living Lab for participatory research and knowledge creation, and linguistic research project OMG showed their practical implementation of data management practices. The lessons shared from Living Lab are that open handling of data, tools and results is still difficult to explain despite the growing Open Science movement, while few questions are asked when one plants to keep data closed; and that participatory sessions require quick ways to record consent and in-situ ethical approaches for data creation. Project OMG showcased Project OMG showcased their standardisation practices using the CHAT transcription format from the Child Language Data Exchange System (CHILDES) project thereby contributing towards the growing database of unified and standardized

CHILDES corpora. Also anonymization and pseudonymisation practices were shown using aliases in text and pencil drawings for video and images.

Supporting researchers with 'no data' in their research, June 2022

Data stewards talked from their own experience how researchers that believe to not use data in their research are supported, and how in own research in the past 'no data' resources could have been managed better. As soon as a file is downloaded, a note made, a book used, there is a resource that needs to be managed. Taking care of notes and documenting, naming and organising all research resources used is essential in any research. A good strategy can be to point out to researchers that the old ways of simply using footnotes and bibliographies to reference sources of information in manuscript may have its limitations in the digital era.

Strategy 3
the limitations of *the old ways*

Here's a list of footnotes

It's all in the big manuscript

I will study primary sources of law, case law, doctrine, soft law, and policy documents

It's all in the bibliography!

What could I have done better?

- I would have taken better care for my own research notes.
- I would have spent more time and effort in documenting my data, including versioning, file naming and folder structure.

Research Project

- Final
- Final0112
- Really final
- This time really really final 0612
- Not yet final
- This is the one
- Yes were there

"FINAL"doc

Network Day 2022

The first year culminated in a live Network Day on 25 February 2022 on the topic "As Open As Possible, As Closed As Needed". Here experts in IP, privacy, ethics and GDPR explained how to address this in practice.

This was followed by interactive break-out sessions based on discipline-specific research use-cases from life sciences, natural sciences or the social sciences, using a set of guiding questions on either IPR issues or privacy law. The aim was to act as data management advisor to the researcher on how best to address all IPR and privacy issues for the research data that would be used and created. Participants discussed responses to the questions and also highlighted further aspects that would need to be clarified with the researcher.

The key takeaway message from the network day was that there is a clear need to discuss, share best practices and exchange experiences on the legal aspects of Open Science.

Live community building days

In a next phase, a series of community building events were organised to take the community to the next level. During four different live days, we brainstormed together about the future of the community and how we can best support our members on a tour through Flanders. Guided by external experts, we started in Brussels with an introduction to the Community Canvas and a game plan on the planned trajectory.

During three events [Identity @ UHasselt](#), [Experience @ KULeuven](#) and [Organisation @ UGent](#) we defined the purpose, values and success criteria of our community, as well as rituals, shared experiences and incentives. These events were each time accompanied with a learning session.

In Brussels we practiced the Lego game developed by the University of Glasgow that can be used for teaching the importance of metadata, data standards and controlled vocabularies for reproducibility.

In Hasselt, a session on teaching techniques was given, followed by a brainstorm on application of these techniques as a data steward.

During the community days in Leuven and Gent, we learned how to use process flows to create a process flow for DMP support.

Community growth

Basecamp is used by the community as a tool for communication and sharing, where discussions have been held on metadata for Dataverse, EOSC data repositories, RDM kit development and ethics for AI and personal data. A working group on de-identification techniques and a technical RDM group have developed as spin-offs from the community.

Our members

Our community is made of RDM support staff (e.g. data stewards) and any other professional with an **active role in supporting and promoting good RDM practices**.

Roles in the community

- General members
- Programme Committee (PC)
- Community manager
- Buddy
- Institutional ambassador or CPOC
- Working group members & leader
- Host institution
- Presenters

Our purpose

The purpose of our community is to **share knowledge, experiences and practices** amongst peers and to do something with it.

We want to bring **tangible outputs** that are immediately applicable to support data stewards. The community helps its members to increase their **confidence** and **efficiency** and bring a **better service for researchers**.

Our values

We share. We exchange knowledge and practice: everytime we meet, we learn something new and practical.

We are open. Anyone with an interest and active role in RDM is welcome to join.

We care. In our job, we support researchers. Here, we support each other.

We grow. Our roles are new, our community too. Together, we decide what we want to be in a continuously evolving landscape.

Success definition

As a community, we are successful when our target group is reached and regularly attends our events; when our **members are engaged and take initiative**; when **our resources are reused and our members recognized** for their expertise and know-how.

Identity

Structure

Experiences

Transition

- General members: no hard exit.
- PC and CPOC: yearly open to rotation

Content and shared experiences

By regular online interaction and organizing 4 yearly live meetings.

- Online: questions & answers, inventory of expertise within our members (who to go), outputs & summaries of our meetings, working documents, final products.
- Live meetings: stories (good & horror), advice, workshops, discussions, definition of priorities & topics.

Rituals

- The torch
- Dixit check-in
- Grabbelton

Incentives

- Visibility: Basecamp, LinkedIn & FRDN websites
- Authorship & citations: WG outputs
- FRDN KH stamp
- Small gifts: presenters, hosts
- Events are fun & useful

Communication & dissemination

- Basecamp: internal communication, project management (e.g. WGs)
- Zenodo community: for finalized outputs

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